

OPTIMIZATION AND SIZING METHODOLOGY OF NECESSARY INFRAESTRUCTURE FOR THE INCORPORATION OF HYDROGEN TO THE TRANSPORTATION SECTOR

Jesús Gallego-Navarro, Emilio Larrodé-Pellicer, Juan Antonio Sicilia-Montalvo, Beatriz Royo-Agustín y Alberto Fraile-del-Pozo

Universidad de Zaragoza, Departamento de Ingeniería Mecánica, Área de Ingeniería e Infraestructura de los Transportes. C/ María de Luna s/n – 50018 Zaragoza. Tfno: +34 976 761888. jesusgallegonavarro@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT:

This study is motivated by the need to develop a methodology that allow the parameterizing of the fuel supply infrastructure needed to drive the new concepts in a transportation system based on electric cars. Among the several electric traction systems, the fuel cell hydrogen vehicle has been identified as the alternative with the greatest potential in the medium to long term to replace conventional vehicles.

At the same time that the emergence of new vehicles with traction systems based on fuel cells and hydrogen technologies, it is necessary the implementation of new infrastructures to ensure the delivery of this new "fuel". Therefore, there is necessity to prepare the arrival of these new infrastructures to the transportation system with the objective that the transition, both in technical and economic terms, is as painless as possible.

Thus, in this study has been performed the analysis and development of a computational tool that allows the use of an optimized design of a new hydrogen distribution infrastructure and of a methodology based on a GIS (Geographic Information System) that allows validate the obtained results with the tool. This make a reality the resolution of the problem of the construction feasibility of resulting number of installations with their technical characteristics in the optimal locations.

Keywords: Hydrogen infrastructure, hydrogen station, transport, GIS, facility sizing

RESUMEN:

El presente estudio viene motivado por la necesidad de desarrollar una metodología que permita la parametrización de la infraestructura de suministro de combustible necesaria para los nuevos conceptos de tracción en un sistema de transporte basado en automóviles eléctricos. De entre los diferentes sistemas de tracción eléctricos, se ha identificado al vehículo de hidrógeno y pila de combustible como la alternativa de mayor potencial a medio-largo plazo para sustituir a los vehículos convencionales.

Paralelamente a la irrupción de nuevos vehículos con sistemas de tracción basados en las tecnologías del hidrógeno y las pilas de combustible, se hace necesaria la implantación de nuevas infraestructuras que aseguren el suministro de este nuevo "combustible". Por lo tanto, se plantea necesario preparar la llegada de estas nuevas infraestructuras al sistema de transporte de forma que la transición, tanto en términos técnicos como económicos, sea lo menos traumática posible. Así, en este estudio se ha realizado el análisis y desarrollo de una herramienta de cálculo que permita la realización de un diseño optimizado de una nueva infraestructura de distribución de hidrógeno y de una metodología basada en un sistema GIS (Sistema de Información Geográfico) que permite validar los resultados obtenidos con la herramienta, posibilitando la resolución del problema de la viabilidad de la construcción de las instalaciones resultantes con sus características técnicas en las ubicaciones más óptimas.

Palabras clave: Infraestructura del hidrógeno, hidrogenera, transporte, GIS, dimensionamiento de instalaciones.

1.- INTRODUCTION

The transportation system provides fundamental social functions, but under current operational conditions cannot be considered as a sustainable system. Transportation system, in part due to the economic growth of emerging countries like China, India and Brazil [1], is responsible for 20% of the expected increase in global energy demand and emissions of greenhouse gases by 2030. At the same time, the economic problem motivated by the end of cheap fossil fuels must be faced. According to experts, the fossil fuels peak production has already overtaken [2].

The transportation sector is one of the major consumers of primary energy; in year 2011 it assumed approximately 28% of primary energy consumption [3] and 22% of global CO₂ emissions, and particularly, road transport is the main

responsible of these consumption and emissions [4]. Therefore, one of the key points in order to achieve a clean environment and fight against the climate change is to get free emissions transportation.

In this direction, the hydrogen fuel cell vehicle complies with zero emissions condition. Hydrogen, which is the most abundant element on the planet, can be used as a clean and efficient fuel. Hydrogen achieves comparable performances to those provided by conventional fossil fuels. Throughout the years, it has been done an extensive research in order to incorporate the hydrogen to the transportation system, especially for medium and long distance applications [5]. Hydrogen is a clean energy carrier and it has a positive impact on climate change, air quality and noise [6, 7].

It is expected that in next 10-20 years the number of hydrogen vehicles will increase significantly. Early years the hydrogen demand will be limited and mainly intended for captive fleets and demonstration projects. Later, the use of hydrogen vehicles will be extended to all consumers [8].

Nowadays, it is not utilized any optimization criterion to locate hydrogen facilities. At the present, hydrogen fleets are located fleets, so its location is decided by proximity criteria; in many cases these facilities are for private use. In this situation, there is a need to create a calculation tool which helps to solve the sizing of hydrogen refueling facilities, according to certain operating, accessibility, availability and viability conditions. With this tool based on a new methodology should be technically and economically evaluated the required hydrogen infrastructure in order to implement in an urban environment a zero emissions transportation system based on hydrogen.

The development of this methodology will help to locate in the most efficient way the hydrogen fueling stations and their size, according to the hydrogen demand along the time and the hydrogen technology deployment. Finding the optimal location, according to both logistical and technical criteria, has great importance due to the high cost of building such facilities.

2.- METODOLOGY

2.1.- SIZING AND OPTIMIZATION TOOL

With the objective of define the hydrogen supply needs and hydrogen infrastructure which are required to provide assistance to a transportation system in an urban environment, has been raised a methodology that provides an evaluation of those available solutions under technical and economic criteria. This methodology works like an assistance tool to the process of decision-making when a new hydrogen infrastructure is planned.

In order to determine the optimal size of the refueling infrastructure, it is necessary to foresee the hydrogen daily demand. If the demand of those fleets of vehicles that are foreseen that are going to use hydrogen in a given horizon of time, or if the study and design of the routes followed by vehicles, in the case of fleets with known routes, are taken into account, it is possible to determine the hydrogen daily demand.

The implanted in a web calculation tool process that has been followed in order to obtain the best option (its general scheme is shown in Figure 1) is the next one:

- Database definition of the. It includes the technical specifications of the greatest possible number of models of all equipment and devices that are in hydrogen refueling or production stations, the greatest number of different vehicles; as well as, the estimated costs of all the considered inputs (orange in Figure 1).
- Determination and simulation of paths and / or estimate fleet that will use the new infrastructure (purple in Figure 1).
- Calculation of the foreseen hydrogen daily demand (blue in Figure 1).
- Input parameter definition: Operation times which affect the total refueling time, filling percentage of vehicle tanks and number of dispensers per hydrogen station. It is needed in order to determine the number of required pumps to meet the total demand. (Included in the process Calculation *No hydrogen stations* in Figure 1).
- Calculation of the number of required hydrogen stations with the aim of meet the calculated hydrogen demand and the number of required pumps. (dark green in Figure 1).

- Selection of technologies to be analyzed as potential for future installations. This takes into account the type of hydrogen demand: state and pressure (light green in Figure 1).
- Combination and attainment of the optimal solution in terms of cost and efficiency among all the technological options that have been previously considered (yellow in Figure 1).

Fig. 1. General scheme of the developed calculation tool

2.1.1.- Optimization criteria of the tool

Prior to the final result provided by the tool, costs and energy efficiencies of the possible technological options will be calculated such criteria to analyze the different technological options and determine which is the optimal. It will take into account: supply (water, energy, gas or hydrogen), production, storage and delivery of hydrogen.

A value will be associated at each option (R_c and R_η for cost and efficiency respectively). This value will vary from one until n ; n represent the number of different options that have been studied. The best option will be n , meanwhile the worst option will be 1. In order to achieve a result which takes into account both criteria, the values associated with each of the options will be added, each multiplied by a weight (λ_c , λ_η), it will take one value or another depending on which want to give more importance to one of the selection criteria, in this case being the optimal choice, as Formula 1, those whose sum (R_T) will be greater.

$$OPTIMAL_CHOICE = MAX (R_T) \quad (1)$$

Where:

$$R_T = (R_{\epsilon} \times \lambda_{\epsilon}) + (R_{\eta} \times \lambda_{\eta}) \quad (2)$$

λ_{ϵ} and λ_{η} , will take values from 0 to 1, depending on the level of importance and will fulfill with the condition indicated in Formula 3.

$$\lambda_{\epsilon} + \lambda_{\eta} = 1 \quad (3)$$

The selection criterion when cost is considered is governed by the function described in Formula 4.

$$f \text{ MIN COST } (COST_{fuel} + COST_{devices} + COST_{energy} + COST_{ext.provisionH_2O}) \quad (4)$$

After applying this function the tool returns all possible technological options for the construction of the refueling station ordered from lowest to highest price (Figure 2).

#	Dispensadores	Respostaje	Almacenamiento	Coste (€/U)	Coste Total(€)
1	H2 Logic 700	gaseoso	HL	1.475.604	1.475.604
2	Hydricity: General Hydrogen 7	gaseoso	HL	1.655.604	1.655.604
3	H2 Logic 700	gaseoso	HCG	2.108.954	2.108.954
4	Hydricity: General Hydrogen 7	gaseoso	HCG	2.288.954	2.288.954
5	H2 Logic 700	gaseoso	HCG	2.469.396	2.469.396
6	Hydricity: General Hydrogen 7	gaseoso	HCG	2.649.396	2.649.396
7	H2 Logic 700	gaseoso	HL	2.725.604	2.725.604

Fig. 2. Results obtained by applying the selection criteria of cost

The selection criterion of performance responds to the function described in Formula 5.

$$f \text{ MAX PERFORMANCE } \left(\eta_{productionH_2} \times \eta_{processes} \times \eta_{ext.provisionH_2} \right) \quad (5)$$

Table 1 shows the performances of the main processes referred in to Formula 5, whose values have been obtained from the query of various sources [9, 10, 11].

PROCESS	EFFICIENCY %
Reforming steam (natural gas)	80
Conventional electrolysis	35*
Liquefaction	55 - 70
Gasification	70
Compression	90
Pipeline transport	80
Transportation cryogenic tank	85
Transportation <i>tube trailer</i>	85

Table 1. Performance of the different processes

* The low efficiency of the electrolysis process is due to the efficiency of the electrolysis itself (56% - 73%) must apply the production's efficiency of electric energy (35% - 55%).

2.2.- GIS SYSTEM

As a complement to the application web which has been developed and faced with the problem of determining the optimal geographical location of hydrogen refueling stations, from the use of a GIS system (shown in gray in Figure 1) has been developed a methodology based on the choice of those criteria that are considered more determinant when siting new facilities, and an allocation of weights based on the importance given to each of these criteria.

The proposed methodology is based on the superposition of layers that allow prioritization or exclusion of certain areas depending on fulfill or not fulfill certain requirements. These layers represent each of the decision criteria considered:

- Average Daily Traffic (ADT)
- Accessibility
- Population density
- Urban transport routes
- Shopping areas
- Industrial areas
- General plan of urban development (GPUD)

Scenes based on urban transport and/or private transport are analyzed:

- Urban Transport:

Special attention is given to the routes taken by the urban buses. In this case it should know the beginning and end of line, the concurrence of line numbers and frequencies in each.

- Private Transport:

In this whole are included private vehicles (cars, vans and motorcycles), taxis, delivery fleets or fleets of municipal vehicles. To optimize location of hydrogen refueling stations should know the areas of highest concentration of vehicles either as origin or destination, or roaming.

The working tool used to develop the methodology is ARCGIS, version 10 under ArcView license.

The information provided is referenced with the same reference system Google Maps "datum WGS84 15N". This makes it possible to represent it through maps in the application and generate the shapefiles corresponding (vector format of digital storage where the location of geographic features and associated attributes are stored).

For the GIS construction, the following plans and their attribute tables that correspond to the common layer information for all scenarios and the different decision criteria are needed:

- Plans of roads in the area under study, with their lengths, number of lanes and directions.
- Plans of Average Daily Traffic (ADT).
- Plans of population density of the city.
- Plans of distribution of commercial activity.
- Plans of distribution of industrial areas.
- Plans of bus lines in the city.
- Plans of General Land-Use Planning of urban development to see the possible buildable parcels.

The road map of the study area or the general plan of urban development divided in their cadastral areas is used as the common information layer. Within each of these areas must be known the ranking and rating, size, cost of land and geolocation.

2.2.1.- Decision Criteria

In order to facilitate decision making on the optimum location of hydrogen refueling stations to provide vehicle fleets have been set some decision criteria and have been associated some weights (ξ_{ADT} , $\xi_{accessibility}$, $\xi_{pop.density}$, ξ_{routes} , $\xi_{shopping}$, $\xi_{industrial}$, ξ_{GPUD}).

2.2.1.1.- Average Daily Traffic

Annual average daily traffic (ADT) is the number of vehicles passing by a road for a year divided by 365. It is considered as the traffic intensity that corresponds to the average day of the year.

The system analyzes the data for the ADT of different pathways and highlighted by a blue trace of a thickness greater the higher is the value of ADT pathway:

ADT > 100,000

ADT between 60,000 and 100,000

ADT between 20,000 and 60,000

Then, as shown in Figure 3, the system highlights an area around greater ADT pathways, so that the higher distance to the road is 200 meters. This area will be considered as preference zone (shown in green in the figures) when locating a refueling station.

Fig. 3. Representation of the main road with ADT ranking and selection according to preferred zones

2.2.1.2.- Accesibility

In order to make the hydrogen refueling station easily accessible, the allocation of the possible locations is realized in intersections, slip roads and crossing roadways with a high level of ADT.

The system analyses the data corresponding to every road and selects the intersection nodes with higher level of AMD. Once these locations are selected, a new layer is created and these nodes are displayed as green circles with the intersection as the center and with a radio of 400 meters, such as are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Selected nodes: intersections with high levels of AMD

2.2.1.3. - Urban transport routes

It considers urban (bus or trams) transport routes. The geolocation of bus stops and tram stops, the starting and the end points of every route must be known because the system uses these data to select the possible locations, (the stop points where more routes converge, the starting and the end point of each one) and it creates another layer where these nodes are displayed by a red circle with 150 meters of radio. The reference frame is the same as the used by Google.

An important addition is being studied and it consists to increase the length of the radios after analyzing the number of vehicles per hour that go through the start and end points of every route. As higher is this number higher will be the radio and the possibility to choose this location. This information would be stored in the data base together with the other attributes of the nodes.

2.2.1.4. - Parcels according to the Land-use planning

The selected locations must be categorized as buildings lands by the Land-Use planning.

The system examines the related information of the selected places in previous steps and creates a new layer where the available building lands are shown.

The previous selected locations that are neither “building lands” nor “industrial park” will be penalized. This penalization is reflected by modifying the weights of each decision criterion.

2.2.1.5. - Residential Areas

Due to the features of the hydrogen, the locations must satisfy safety requirements as maintain the minimum distance among the hydrogen refueling stations and the selected areas.

In this research the minimum distance between the residential areas and the possible location is upper 300 meters. This amount is greater than the considered in previous studies: for instance in [12] establishes a safety perimeter of 200 meters.

The classification of the areas according to the population density is very useful to decide the optimal locations. As higher is this measure, higher is the probability to the traffic density being greater. On this way it is proved the tight relation among the population density and the AMD.

Such as it is shown in the Figure 5, a new layer with the excluded areas (red) is created. These areas represent the residential areas with an added perimeter of 300 meters.

Fig. 5. Excluded areas as result of considering the residential locations

2.2.1.6. - Commercial districts

The commercial districts gather a high level of traffic. On one hand, they assemble a big amount of customers and visitors and on the other hand, they generate a continuous flow of employees and freight transportation.

Once the places with a higher level of commercial activity have been stored, the system creates a layer similar to the previous one. In this case the excluded places house the commercial districts with an added perimeter of 500 meters and they are enclosed by a green ring with 200 meters of width, because they generate a high crowd of traffic and these areas are considered as available. In the Figure 6, the excluded area surrounded by the eligible area is shown.

Fig. 6. Excluded areas (red) and preferent areas (green) because of the presence of commercial districts

2.2.1.7.- Industrial Parks

In the same way that commercial districts, these areas assemble a big amount of customers and continuous movements of employees and freight causing high level of traffic.

Fig. 7. Industrial parks located in the studied region

In the Figure 7, the layer with the possible locations in industrial parks is displayed by the system after these data have been stored. The number of available areas to consider is the same as the number of industrial parks.

2.2.2.- Optimal Location selection

After analyzing all the decision criteria, it is proceeded to the selection of optimal locations. From the decision criteria, the layers that represent the areas of exclusion (red) and preference (green) for the location of the hydrogen stations are generated. Preference areas that overlap the exclusion are automatically rejected.

Fig. 8. Decision criteria introduced on the base map and areas of exclusion and preference generated.

Each decision criterion is accompanied by a weight that is used to decide between all possible, the position of the optimum locations. Owing to commercial areas generate two areas: an internal area of exclusion and other external area of preference, two different weights are associated: $\xi_{shopping1}$ and $\xi_{shopping2}$ respectively. On the Table 2 are summarized the decision criteria with its corresponding identifier and its associated weight. Table 3 summarizes the values assigned to the weights associated to the different decision criteria.

Decision criterion	Area factor	Weight
ADT	C_{ADT}	ξ_{ADT}
Accessibility	$C_{accessibility}$	$\xi_{accessibility}$
Urban transport routes	C_{routes}	ξ_{routes}
Commercial areas (internal area)	$C_{shopping1}$	$\xi_{shopping1}$
Commercial areas (external area)	$C_{shopping2}$	$\xi_{shopping2}$
Industrial areas	$C_{industrial}$	$\xi_{industrial}$
GPUD	C_{GPUD}	ξ_{GPUD}
Population density	$C_{pop.density}$	$\xi_{pop.density}$

Table 2. Summary of decision criteria and associated weights

The weights of the criteria implicating the creation of preference areas will have positive values. The value of these weights will range between 0 and 1, but it must satisfy that the sum of them is equal to 1, as is reflected in Formula 6. The considered location as ideal would take this value.

The associated weights with the decision criteria taking positive value are: ADT (ξ_{ADT}), Accessibility ($\xi_{accessibility}$), Urban transport routes (ξ_{routes}), Commercial areas ($\xi_{shopping2}$), Industrial areas ($\xi_{industrial}$) y GPUD (ξ_{GPUD}).

$$\xi_{ADT} + \xi_{accessibility} + \xi_{routes} + \xi_{shopping2} + \xi_{industrial} + \xi_{GPUD} = 1 \quad (6)$$

The weights of the criteria implicating the creation of exclusion areas will have the value (-1).

The associated weights with the decision criteria taking negative value are: Commercial areas ($\xi_{commercial1}$) y Population density ($\xi_{pop.density}$).

Weight	Values
ξ_{ADT}	0.05
$\xi_{accessibility}$	0.05
ξ_{routes}	0.05
$\xi_{shopping1}$	-1
$\xi_{shopping2}$	0.05
$\xi_{industrial}$	0.4
ξ_{GPUD}	0.4
$\xi_{pop.density}$	-1

Table 3. Values assigned to the weights associated to the different decision criteria

To determine the priority order of the possible locations for new installations, the process to follow is:

- sum of the products of the area factors (C_i) by their associated weights (ξ_i) in areas where preference areas are overlapped, which categorize the area with a number that is denominated decision degree (Formula 7):

$$Decision\ degree = \sum_i^j (C_i * \xi_i) \quad (7)$$

The area factors (C_i) corresponding to the different decision criteria will have the value 1 or 0, in function of if the system recognizes exclusion areas or preference areas on the study areas.

According to the criterion established so that an area be considered as possible, the decision degree must be greater or equal to 0.4. In the case of it is equal or less than zero, the area is automatically rejected to being affected by an exclusion area. In the case of the result is between 0 and 0.4 (both values are excluded), means that the area is designated as not for building.

- b) When the decision degree is greater or equal to 0.4, to greater value of this number, more optimal will be the possible location.

3.- RESULTS

Applying the web tool developed, the most economical option of the technically feasible in the case of vehicles that store hydrogen as a gas at high pressure, it is that contemplates an infrastructure based on external supply of hydrogen in gas state.

The intermediate results obtained on the calculation web tool referred to the number of hydrogen stations to install and its dimensions (depending on the equipment and the technology that will be assembled), will be the reference data to use by the GIS methodology developed to determinate the location optimal among the possible.

Such as shown in Figure 9, as a result of the methodology followed by the GIS system, it will be obtained green areas that represent areas in which it is feasible to locate the new installations resulting from the overlapping of the preference areas generated by the different decision criteria.

Fig. 9. Representation of the optimum areas for the location of the hydrogen supply stations

4.- DISCUSSION

With the methodology exposed in this paper is possible to determine on the one hand, the optimal size and number of hydrogen fueling installations to build, and on the other hand, the most suitable technology option in function of technical and economic criteria; and additionally, obtain a classification of the possible locations for these installations within a given area. Thus a global solution that serves as an aid to decision making for managers to manage this type of installations is provided.

In other studies also have attempted to respond to the various problems described in this paper, but it has not identified any methodology covering all complete problem. For example, there are models that analyze the different alternatives of production, storage and distribution of hydrogen and that calculate the capital cost of infrastructures and the transport of hydrogen for each of the options studied [13], or that analyze and compare qualitatively the production and distribution systems for different scenarios of demand and time [14]. The problem of the location of the network of hydrogen stations is usually treated as a simple problem of locating installations in a road network or as if it were a subset of the existing network of stations [15, 16, 17]. Other solutions use the problem of "fuel travel back," based on the premise that where more people drive is where going to arise the need for refueling [18].

GIS systems are also used, but contrary to what is pretended in this study are not related with the dimensioning and technical and economic optimization of installations. For example, there are models that combine GIS systems and

genetic algorithms to process data, analyze scenarios, introduce assumptions and get results on a map; in [19] a network of hydrogen infrastructure is designed by the introduction a network of roads with speed limits, the volume of flow between each origin and destination, the maximum possible distance between hydrogen stations and the number of installations to build. However, the number of criteria used is less than that considered in this study.

In [20] is done a review of the factors involved in the introduction of hydrogen in the transport sector and it is identified the price of hydrogen, the capital costs of infrastructure, the role of administrations and the capacity factors (production modes and the transport of hydrogen in terms of penetration rates of these technologies) as the most crucial; factors are also considered in form relevant in this study.

5.- CONCLUSIONS

The proposed methodology makes possible to achieve some initial configurations about the hydrogen infrastructure that is necessary to meet the needs of a new transportation fleet based on hydrogen. These solutions, classified by technical and economic criteria, are helpful in the initial stage of decision making.

The incorporation of this methodology to a web tool with a database containing different models of those devices which are present in the different combinations of technologies produces results quickly. It facilitates the analysis of different solutions and changes in the technological combinations previously obtained in order to achieve the optimal solution in cost and efficiency.

Essential input prior to determining the optimal size of hydrogen refuelling stations is the expected hydrogen daily demand. It can be calculated from:

- Expected vehicle fleet hydrogen demand, public or private, which will use hydrogen in a determined time horizon. It is an estimate option based on the allocation of demand depending on the number of vehicles: cars, vans, buses or trucks.
- In the case of captive or private fleets with known distances, the study and design of the routes followed by vehicles. In this case, expected hydrogen demands are much closer to reality.

When designing the calculation tool, the most sensitive point both for technical and economical reasons, is the choice of hydrogen supply source to the station. It depends on four variables: cost, demand, location of facilities and security of supply.

A GIS system that reflects the modelling of the transport system and a set of decision criteria help to determine the size, characteristics and location of the network of hydrogen refuelling stations that minimizes the cost function and maximizes the operativity and functionality one.

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